

Identification of Wet Troposphere Delay in L-band InSAR Measurements: Delta-X UAVSAR InSAR measurement QA masks.

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Short description: This document contains figures showing a series of QA masks of troposphere-induced phase delay regions that were generated for all SAR acquisitions from the NASA Delta-X mission using a weather feature matching algorithm as explained in (Oliver-Cabrera et al., 2024, submitted to Journal of Geodesy). The QA masks were formed by analyzing the interferometric phases and feature matching them against NOAA NEXRAD weather radar images. The masks are classified in 3 categories: 0 for clear sky, 1 for weather feature presence with possible troposphere-phase delay and 2 for areas where tropospheric phase delay was matched to a weather radar feature for the case of InSAR domain QA masks. For the case of SAR domain QA masks regions classified as 2 are those that were consistently detected across all interferograms related to a particular acquisition.

Abstract from Oliver-Cabrera et al., 2024, submitted to Journal of Geodesy:

Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) pulses undergo variable delays in the atmosphere due to pressure, temperature, and humidity changes in the troposphere, posing a major source of error in InSAR measurements. Wet troposphere delay, caused by condensed water and water vapor clouds, can cause delays of tens of centimeters that significantly impact surface displacement estimates. Our study employs a feature-comparison method using NOAA NEXRAD weather radar station reflectivity data to identify artifacts from wet tropospheric delays in InSAR phase measurements derived from rapid repeat-pass data collected with the UAVSAR L-band SAR. NEXRAD's 5-minute scanning interval, compared to UAVSAR's 30-minute revisit time, enabled detection of phase artifacts caused by fast-moving and developing clouds. We identify regions in InSAR interferograms with troposphere-induced phase artifacts by matching features common to InSAR phase outlier masks and NEXRAD high reflectivity masks. Matched results between InSAR phase noise and NEXRAD reflectivity show phase delays of up to 25 radians in L-band, corresponding to 48 cm of delay. Comparison with tropospheric delays calculated using the Generic Atmospheric Correction Online Service for InSAR (GACOS) showed that the weather model has insufficient spatial and temporal resolution to accurately estimate the observed wet troposphere delays. While our study focused on UAVSAR, the findings are applicable to other SAR missions, including the L-band NISAR mission, aiding identification and interpretation of InSAR results affected by tropospheric delays.

Data location and description:

The full Delta-X dataset, including the QA masks summarized in this document, can be found at the Oak Ridge National Laboratory Distributed Active Archive Center (ORNL DAAC) (https://daac.ornl.gov/cgi-bin/dataset_lister.pl?p=41). Mask files are stored at the DAAC as Int16 ENVI .dat binary raster files that include a .hdr header file per file. Although the previews shown throughout this report are shown in radar coordinates, the files at the DAAC are geocoded and compatible with GIS software.

Spring Campaign

Total InSAR domain masks: 303

Total SAR domain masks: 137

atchaf_06309_210327

InSAR

NEXRAD

InSAR domain QA masks

SAR domain QA masks

atchaf_06309_210401

InSAR

NEXRAD

InSAR domain QA masks

SAR domain QA masks

atchaf_06309_210402

InSAR

NEXRAD

InSAR domain QA masks

SAR domain QA masks

atchaf_19809_210327

InSAR

NEXRAD

InSAR domain QA masks

SAR domain QA masks

atchaf_19809_210401

InSAR

NEXRAD

InSAR domain QA masks

SAR domain QA masks

atchaf_19809_210402

InSAR

NEXRAD

InSAR domain QA masks

SAR domain QA masks

eterre_08705_210412

InSAR

NEXRAD

InSAR domain QA masks

SAR domain QA masks

eterre_08705_210416

InSAR

NEXRAD

InSAR domain QA masks

SAR domain QA masks

eterre_08705_210418

InSAR

NEXRAD

InSAR domain QA masks

SAR domain QA masks

eterre_27309_210412

InSAR

NEXRAD

InSAR domain QA masks

SAR domain QA masks

eterre_27309_210416

InSAR

NEXRAD

InSAR domain QA masks

SAR domain QA masks

etterre_27309_210418

InSAR

InSAR masked

NEXRAD

InSAR domain QA masks

SAR domain QA masks

wterre_16300_210405

InSAR

NEXRAD

InSAR domain QA masks

SAR domain QA masks

wterre_16300_210406

InSAR

NEXRAD

InSAR domain QA masks

SAR domain QA masks

wterre_16300_210407

InSAR

NEXRAD

InSAR domain QA masks

SAR domain QA masks

wterre_34202_210405

InSAR

NEXRAD

InSAR domain QA masks

SAR domain QA masks

wterre_34202_210406

InSAR

NEXRAD

InSAR domain QA masks

SAR domain QA masks

wterre_34202_210407

InSAR

NEXRAD

InSAR domain QA masks

SAR domain QA masks

Fall Campaign

Total InSAR domain masks: 178

Total SAR domain masks: 83

atchaf_06309_210905

InSAR

InSAR masked

NEXRAD

InSAR domain QA masks

SAR domain QA masks

atchaf_06309_210913

InSAR

NEXRAD

InSAR domain QA masks

SAR domain QA masks

atchaf_19809_210905

InSAR

NEXRAD

InSAR domain QA masks

SAR domain QA masks

atchaf_19809_210913

InSAR

NEXRAD

InSAR domain QA masks

SAR domain QA masks

etterre_08705_210904

InSAR

InSAR masked

NEXRAD

InSAR domain QA masks

SAR domain QA masks

eterre_08705_210907

InSAR

NEXRAD

InSAR domain QA masks

SAR domain QA masks

etterre_27309_210904

InSAR

InSAR masked

NEXRAD

InSAR domain QA masks

SAR domain QA masks

etterre_27309_210907

InSAR

NEXRAD

InSAR domain QA masks

SAR domain QA masks

wterre_16300_210903

InSAR

InSAR masked

NEXRAD

InSAR domain QA masks

SAR domain QA masks

wterre_16300_210912

InSAR

InSAR masked

NEXRAD

InSAR domain QA masks

SAR domain QA masks

wterre_34202_210903

InSAR

InSAR masked

NEXRAD

InSAR domain QA masks

SAR domain QA masks

wterre_34202_210912

InSAR

InSAR masked

NEXRAD

InSAR domain QA masks

SAR domain QA masks

